

PORTFOLIO BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The current article describes what Portfolio based approach is, the types of portfolios as well as their structures. It is one of the effective ways to bring variety into the classroom in terms of instructions as well as develop the students' learning ability.*

Keywords: *portfolio, evaluation, information resources, learner autonomy, self-reflection*

Foreign language acquisition is one the tasks put forward by the government of Uzbekistan for the sake of the development of the nation. For this reason, much research is being done in the sphere of methodology. One of the approaches that motivates teachers to modify their instructional practices so that the learners will be able to think creatively and share what they are learning and how is the Portfolio Based Approach. It is also an effective way to challenge the learners to motivate to learn as it brings some variety to the teaching process rather than sitting and doing the exercises given in the textbooks.

According to Yang (2003), a portfolio is a student work compilation that demonstrates their attempts, learning progress, and accomplishments as well as their thoughts on the portfolio entries.) The primary objectives of portfolios are to increase the learners' degree of motivation and encourage them to learn independently in the process of language acquisition. (Güngör, 2005: 17) states that a student's portfolio is a compilation of their academic achievements that demonstrate their efforts, advancement, and triumphs within their educational programs in accordance with specific goals.

Referring to Arter and Spandel (1991), A portfolio is a carefully curated collection of student work which displays their efforts or accomplishment in one or different fields. Portfolio is supposed to include the evidence for student reflection, his contribution in selecting the content and criteria for merit. According to Grace (1992, p. 1), points out that argues that a learner's complete learning experience is documented in a portfolio, including what he thinks, questions, analyzes, synthesizes, produces, creates, and engages intellectually, emotionally, and socially with others, as well as what he has learned and how she went about learning.

According to Magnan (1985), portfolio is an effective tool for developing students' writing skills as they communicate ideas, feelings, opinions, thoughts, and attitudes. Also, they will be able to work on grammar items, lexical resource, and spelling. Writing in a foreign language also serves the educational purposes of learning, communication, fluency, imitation, reinforcement, and training (Raimes, 1987). Portfolio-based writing evaluations have drawn a lot of attention in colleges and universities because they integrate teaching, learning, and assessment both within and beyond disciplines in the college curriculum. According to Scarcella and Oxford (1995), writing in a foreign language aids learners in improving their grammatical, strategic, and sociolinguistic abilities in the target language.

Characteristics of Portfolio

The following traits frequently occur during the portfolio assessment process: - It is continuous and ongoing, providing opportunities for summative (i.e., culminating) and formative (i.e., ongoing) evaluations of students' advancement toward key outcomes.

- It is multidimensional, showcasing a range of products and procedures that depict many facets of students' learning processes.

- It allows for collaborative reflection, including ways for students to reflect on their own thinking processes and meta cognitive introspection, as they track their own understanding, consider their approaches to problem-solving and making decisions, and keep track of their evolving understanding of topics and skills.

There is no set structure or material for a portfolio because they vary depending on their function. What should be included will depend on the course's objectives and content. The researchers distinguish between several sorts of portfolios as a result of these problems. There are five different categories of portfolios, according to Haladyn (1997), including the ideal, showcase, documentation, assessment, and class portfolios.

In ideal portfolios students are supposed to include all their works done throughout the course and it is not graded. the point here the students themselves assess their own portfolio and it serves as a self-assessment tool.

Only the best works produced by the students are included in the showcase portfolio. The selection of their own works is something that students should do on their own. These portfolios should not be used for assessment or grading.

The Documentation portfolio consists of a series of projects over time that show development and demonstrate students' comprehension of predetermined outcomes. Quality and quantity statistics are gathered by students.

A typical selection of student work is included in the evaluation portfolio, which may be chosen by the teacher or, in some situations, by the student. This portfolio is appropriate for student evaluation. The student's grade, the teacher's perspective, and information about the students in the class are all included in the portfolio. This portfolio meets the criteria for a class portfolio.

It is evident that academics distinguish between several portfolio types based on their objectives and composition. In addition to the portfolios mentioned above, more types of portfolios can be mentioned. It is challenging to distinguish between these, though. On the other hand, the aforementioned portfolios can be utilized singly or in combination with other portfolios. Teachers should choose the appropriate ones and use them.

As for the structure of the portfolio, the learner organizes the items he has selected in the portfolio, which serves as a storage container. Sections are the broad groups of materials that make up the portfolio. There may be headings inside the three sections to assist organize the content and establish the section's structure in which the categories can be obligatory and optional. Material that is essentially significant for a specific portfolio is included under mandatory headings. The quantity of Mandatory headings ought to be carefully limited, required, and adequate to reflect the portfolio's attributes. The content, structure, and volume of the portfolio can be customized by using freely assigned headings. The portfolio structure was established once and for all, although it is not fixed. Depending on the type of portfolio and the particulars of the topic being studied, the teacher and students decide on the number of sections and titles, their subject matter, and their intended substance. As they get more adept at organizing their portfolios, it might shift. The

following sections should be included in the portfolio when creating the final edition to provide structure and ease.

Table 1

Sections of portfolio

Section 1.	Portrait
Section 2.	Information resources
Section 3.	Working materials
Section 4.	Achievements

Each of the sections may contain smaller structural elements—headings. The "Portrait" section is intended to provide information about the student. The author of the portfolio has the opportunity to present himself by creating a personal web page, an electronic resume, or self-presentation in the Power Point program. It also should have “Cover letter” from the portfolio owner including a brief explanation of the document's structure and its purpose.

Headings in the portfolios are structural components that can be found in each section. Information about the student is to be provided in the "Portrait" section. The creator of the portfolio has the option to advertise themselves by setting up a personal website, an electronic resume, or a Power Point presentation. This section must have a heading with an introduction piece that justifies the goal of the portfolio's creation, the inclusion of particular items, and the outcomes of the activities those materials are meant to represent.

The "Information Resources" section is the one that contains the student-selected information relevant to the theme of the portfolio. Students' online research for this portion, including the use of electronic encyclopedias and educational resources like audio and video materials, is a key component of this section. The teacher may provide the student with materials in this section, such as instructions, memos, diagrams, or a list of books on a certain subject. Some of the data; eventually, might be archived or used in another portfolio.

The section "Working Materials" contains the materials that students create and organize in the process of preparing for and completing specific tasks. These materials include graphic materials (tables, graphs, and a list of relevant literature), texts for messages and reports, a variety of creative works, finished control and independent work, materials on the student's project activities, etc.

The last section, "Achievements," contains works that, in the view of the student, show his or her proficiency in academic activity. These include tests that have been passed, laboratory work that has been successfully performed, feedback from instructors and peers, certificates, etc. A reflexive note explaining why the student believes this work to be his prior must be present on each piece of content in this section.

In conclusion, various portfolio types are classified according to their goals and content. More portfolio types can be mentioned in addition to those that were already discussed. The aforementioned portfolios, however, can be used independently or in conjunction with other portfolios. Teachers ought to pick the best ones and apply them in the teaching process according to the aim of the course so as to monitor student’s performance and achieve efficiency in the teaching process.

REFERENCES

1. Arter, J., & Spandel, V. (1991). Using portfolios of student work in instruction and assessment. Portland, OR: Northwest Regional Educational Laboratory
2. Güngör, S. (2005). Ortaöğretim geometri dersi üçgenler konusunda oluşturmacı (constructivism) yaklaşıma dayalı elle yapılan materyaller ve portfolyo (portfolio) hazırlamanın öğrenciler üzerindeki etkilerinin incelenmesi. Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Zonguldak Karaelmas Üniversitesi, Zonguldak.
3. Haladyna, T.M. (1997). Writing Test Items to Evaluate Higher Order Thinking. USA: Allyn & Bacon.
4. Magnan, S. S. (1985). Teaching and testing proficiency in writing: Skills to transcend the second-language classroom. In Alice C. Omaggio, (Ed.), Proficiency, curriculum, articulation: The ties that bind. Northeast Conference Reports, 109-136. Middlebury, VT: Northeast Conference.
5. Paulson, F. L., Paulson, P. R., & Meyer, C. A. (1991, February). What makes a portfolio a portfolio? Educational Leadership, 46 (5), 60-63.
6. Raimes, A. (1987). Why write? From purpose to pedagogy. English Teaching Forum, 25(4), 36-41
7. Scarcella, R. C., & Oxford, R. L. (1992). The tapestry of language learning: The individual in the communicative classroom. Boston: Heinle & Heinle Publishers.
8. Yang, N. D. (2003). Integrating portfolios into learning strategy-based instruction for EFL college students. IRAL, 41(4), 293-317. Retrieved December 7, 2009, from Education Full Text (Wilson).
9. Grace, C. (1992). The Portfolio and Its Use: Developmentally Appropriate Assessment of Young Children. Eric Digest. ED351150